

Monitoring PFAS in Valencia's Sewage System and Wastewater Treatment Plant

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Abstract

Concern about micropollutants in water has grown due to their toxicity and health effects. In this regard, the MORESAN project studies the presence and evolution of microplastics, ARGs, pathogens, PFAS, antibiotics and other pharmaceutical products in sewerage from Valencia city and its evolution in the wastewater treatment plant. The present work presents preliminary results of the MORESAN project regarding PFAS. Analyses show the predominance of PFPeA, PFHxA, PFOA, PFTrDA in the sewage. In the wastewater treatment some PFAS (PFPeA, PFOS and PFHxA) persist after treatment, with higher concentrations in summer. There is still no clear trend to the efficiency of WWTP eliminating these substances, highlighting the need for increasing our efforts in monitor them and understand their behaviour.

Keywords (maximum 6 in alphabetical order)

Micropollutants, PFAS, sewage water, WWTP

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the scientific community has become increasingly concerned about the effect that, the so called micropollutants present in water, may have on human health and the environment. They are, at very low concentrations, toxic, carcinogenic or endocrine disruptors (Mishra et al., 2023). Advances in analytical chemistry and biotechnology allow the detection of an increasingly high number of substances included in this term: residues of pharmaceuticals, microplastics, additives associated with them and even antibiotic resistant genes (ARGs). An effective approach for monitoring polluted water community-wide is wastewater-based epidemiology (WBE) approach, used to provide health and lifestyle information on the study population (Lorenzo et al., 2019). On this behalf sewage wastewater and wastewater treatment plants play an important role in monitoring those micropollutants. As it is reflected in the current regulation (EU, 2022), need arise to control the concentration of emerging pollutants that may not be eliminated in WWTPs.

In this sense, the MORESAN project is focused on detecting, identifying, quantifying and statistically characterize different emerging contaminants including antibiotics, other commonly used pharmaceutical products, antibiotic resistant ARGs and other contaminants of interest such as per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAs). These contaminants are analysed in 12 points from urban wastewater in the city of Valencia and their evolution as a result of wastewater treatment processes. With the analytical measurements is possible to stablish correlations between emerging pollutants and the well-known analytics daily done (COD, SS, nutrients, pH). The sociological factor is included in all these analyses to study if there is a difference in the pollutant distribution. In this work we focus our results on the analyses of the concentration, distribution and evolution of PFAs for the three analytical campaigns done so far. PFAS are a group of synthetic organic chemicals extensively used in consumer and industrial applications over the past decades. These synthetic chemicals, derived from human processes, include organofluoride surfactants characterized by strong fluorinated carbon covalent bonds. As a result, they exhibit exceptional resistance to degradation and oxidation due to their hydrophobic and oleophobic nature, as well as their chemical and mechanical stability consequently, they persist in the environment for an extended period (Reddy et al., 2024).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A total of 12 sampling points have been established in the sewage network of the city of Valencia, these being considered the minimum number of points for the analysis to be representative. Four main criteria were used to select these points, 1. Socioeconomic parameters; 2. Spatial distribution of the points in the study area; 3. Proximity to hospitals; 4. Accessibility for sampling. The final sampling points to be studied were established, obtaining the catchment basin of each point and inflow zone (Figure 1). Two points were established to specifically study the sewage water coming from a hospital (black basin in Figure 1).

Figure 1. Distribution of the sampling points and the sub-basins represented in these points. In each basin, points with the same colour represent where the sample is collected.

Likewise, 6 points were established to analyse the fate of the pollutants in the WWTP of Pinedo, Valencia. This WWTP treats the vast majority of the wastewater in Valencia: P.1. Influent wastewater; P.2. Secondary settling outlet; P.3. WWTP effluent (tertiary treatment outlet); P.4. Mixed sludge entering to the anaerobic digester; P.5. Digested sludge; P.6. Dewatered sludge. The analytics made were the following: traditional physicochemical for wastewater, metals, PFAS, antibiotics and ARGs. Three analytical campaigns have been carried out so far, corresponding with different climate scenarios (February, May and July). The extraction of PFAs from water samples was made using solid-phase extraction (SPE) coupled with high-performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS/MS). Each PFAs is quantified and confirmed using compound-specific transitions. A semi-automated workflow and an internal standard calibration curve enable accurate concentration estimation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The current results represent the preliminary three sampling campaigns carried out so far. When examining the distribution of PFAS by sampling campaigns in each sampling point (Figure 2A), PFAS concentrations in the third sampling (July) reached higher values than in first (February) and second (May) sampling campaigns. This could indicate an increase in PFAS concentrations in summer, however, further sampling is needed to confirm this trend. To examine the distribution of PFAS by sampling points (Figure 2B), PFAS concentration at each point are summed and averaged over the three samples (from sewage and WWTP points). Except from 3 points (Nazaret, La Fe Norte (hospital), and Cortes), sewage concentrations are lower than the inlet of WWTP. The concentration at the outlet of the WWTP is just slightly lower than at the influent, however, more campaigns are needed to confirm these low PFAS removal.

Figure 2. Total PFAs concentration of each sampling point in sewage water of the three sampling campaigns (A). Total concentration in the sampling points comparing with the WWTP entrance and effluent (B).

By frequency of occurrence, in the sewage, all PFAS appear at least once in all the samplings campaigns, but PFPeA, PFHxA, PFOA, PFTrDA stand out, appearing 61%, 56%, 56% and 64% respectively of 36 measurements done (Figure 3A). This frequency is higher than the one shown in the entrance of the WWTP (Figure 3B), what is more, three of them have never been detected over the quantification level in the WWTP in any of the 3 measurements done: PFDA and PFTeDA. This could be due to the dilution contribution from de wastewaters of the rest of the city or the great reactivity of the PFAs between themselves.

Figure 3. Frequency of the PFAs in the sewage water (A) and in the entrance and effluent of WWTP (B).

When focusing on the average concentration of each PFA, taking into account all the 12 points sampled in the city in the three samplings performed (Figure 4), it is observed that three of them present concentrations higher than the rest in the sewage water, these being PFPeA, PFHxA, PFOA and PFTrDA. The ones with higher concentration coincide with the ones of high frequencies.

Figure 4. Average PFAS concentrations in the sewage water sampled in the 12 city points during the 3 sampling campaigns done.

The preliminary results of the evolution in the WWTP (Figure 5) shown that some PFAS are hardly detected (PFTeDA, PFDA and PFNA), while others, such as PFPeA, PFOS and PFHxA, are systematically detected in all three samplings. Although in general it appears that PFAS concentrations are lower at the WWTP outlet, this is not true for all PFASs in all three campaigns. Although the concentration of PFOS is higher at the effluent than at the influent of the WWTP, this is due to the fact that in the first sampling a large amount was detected, but it can be seen that in the other two samplings this is not the case. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out more sampling campaigns to clarify this trend.

Figure 5. Evolution of PFAS in the WWTP. Figure A, B and C represent first, second and third sampling campaign.

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